

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ:
ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT COMPETENCE OF SCHOOL

DIRECTORS IN IMPROVING THE QUALIFICATIONS OF TEACHERS

Mamataliyeva Umida Xushboqovna

SAMDVCHBU TF

Anotation: This article highlights the relevance and stages of effective organization of post-qualification activities of educational institution leaders, which is considered the most important issue of management activity in the public education system, and the tasks of leaders in ensuring the quality of education.

The social reforms carried out during the years of independence serve to create the necessary conditions for rapid development in all spheres of society, for sovereign Uzbekistan to take a worthy place in the world infrastructure. Qualified specialists and potential leaders have a special role in the positive changes taking place in the social, economic and cultural spheres. After all, it is only with their efforts that it is possible to inspire the team to labor victories and show examples of selflessness. According to the national personnel training program, personnel qualification improvement and retraining is considered an independent type of education. An important link of the continuing education system - the professional development system - focuses on the consistent development of the intellectual potential of personnel operating in various spheres of public life. Because the ability of pedagogues to correctly interpret the essence of events is of decisive importance in the reflection of the social changes taking place in society under the influence of scientific, technical and technological processes in the educational content. This means that in modern conditions there is a social need for leaders to be able to deeply feel their professional, leadership potential, management responsibility. At the same time, it is possible to assess the current situation by determining how effective managers can be in organizing management activities after the training course. Training is a stage of theoretical and methodical preparation of specialists in accordance with social changes, modern scientific achievements, so that they can work in accordance with the requirements of the time by updating and improving their professional knowledge and skills. The process after the advanced training course is a special stage of the general professional activity, which represents the direct application of modern professional knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in the advanced training course by specialists

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and managers of the fields, and is a factor that guarantees the quality and effectiveness of education. The main goal of the State National Program for the Development of School Education is primarily to provide schools in rural areas with qualified pedagogical personnel, to improve the quality of their composition, to create an effective system of training and professional development of teachers, and to strengthen the promotion of teachers' work. If we pay serious attention to this issue, we will understand that it imposes huge responsibilities, demands and tasks on the heads of educational institutions. Nowadays, one of the most urgent problems is the activity of pedagogues after the training course. The quality and efficiency achieved as a result of professional development are, first of all, qualitative changes in the knowledge, skills and abilities of students, and secondly, the use of interactive methods of education by teachers in the course of the lesson, the practical application of the innovations acquired during the professional development course, school pedagogical councils. It can be seen in production meetings, demonstration of the innovations obtained in the course at method associations, seminars held at the district and city level, open classes, school Olympiads, and active participation in science months and extracurricular activities organized at the school. For this purpose, it is necessary to properly organize the post-training activities of the heads of educational institutions in the training system. In the process of implementing the requirements of the Law " On Education" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the National Program of Personnel Training, increasing the effectiveness of post-course activities of general secondary educational institutions leaders, enabling them to work in a new way, to independently search for themselves. teaching, created the need to pay attention to the creation of the necessary conditions for effective assimilation of advanced pedagogical technologies by them. Based on the current requirements and needs, raising the quality of the leader's activities after the training course to a new level in the educational process, forming independent education skills and qualifications during this period creates an opportunity to organize a high professional level of management. The stages of implementation of the approximate project of the personal work plan program of the head of the school should be as follows: - work on the basis of the general problem of the school; - making a list of literature on the selected topic. Compiling their annotated index card, enriching the list of literature with new ones. - introduce innovations in the management of school education based on the recommendations and instructions

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given during the training process; - use of pedagogical technologies in management;

- giving lectures about the work done by the school pedagogical council and the district educational council of the educational institution; - covering the carried out work and research in the press; - to increase the efficiency of the management staff during the training course; - use of advanced pedagogical technologies, regularly conducting and observing open classes in order to improve the professional skills of pedagogues. Also, it is one of the important requirements that the heads of general secondary schools should be equipped with tools that will allow them to effectively increase their management activities after the advanced training course. Documents such as diagnosis map, diary, correspondence, inquiry letter, response letter to inquiry letter, offer letter, response letter to offer letter, biography, questionnaire, test, questionnaire and recommendation, work papers, management efficiency. serves to increase. In practice, the heads of general secondary schools confirm the need to pay special attention to the further development of the skills of effective, active work with the above-mentioned documents and work papers after the training course. Thus, as a process, it represents the coverage of all functions and areas of activity by leaders in the organization of management activities after the training course. Leaders, like any other process, should organize practical actions to increase the efficiency of management activity in the period after the training course, relying on scientific, theoretical and practical ideas based on certain requirements. This requirement is met by the development of a thorough post-training development program by managers. The high level of the development program from an ideological point of view, and its compatibility with practice depends on the spiritual and moral aspects, worldview, leadership skills, skills and experience of the heads of general secondary schools. Based on the above opinions,

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analysis of work related to the improvement of management activities carried out by the heads of all types of educational institutions, including general secondary schools, selection of personnel for pedagogical team leaders, training , we came to the conclusion that further development of the ability to effectively manage spiritual-educational and innovative processes is one of the important tasks of the professional development system.

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